

Preferred Teaching Practices among Junior High School Teachers and its Impact towards Readiness of Grade Seven Students in the Secondary School

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ABSTRACT

The primary objective of this study is to examine and identify the preferred teaching practices among selected Grade 7 junior high school subject teachers and its impact and effectiveness towards readiness of incoming Grade 7 students in the secondary school conducted at Espiritu Santo Parochial School of Manila, Inc. using the sequential mixed method design. The participants of this study were determined through purposive convenience sampling. In terms of the readiness among Grade 7 students, subject teachers identified teaching practices to address specific approaches in the transitional stage of the students from elementary (primary school) to junior high school (secondary school); both quantitative and qualitative methods were implemented in a sequential manner, through a survey (first phase) and an interview (second phase). The researchers also asked permission to the participants to give necessary existing data, the class mean of their respective sections both in the first and second grading periods to assess whether the teaching practices are effective and suitable for the students. The data are analyzed using the frequency, percentage, rank, and average distribution in determining the intensity of the response for each indicator in the survey questionnaire, and the content analysis based on the interview. Hake factor analysis is also used to obtain the normalized gain in analyzing and interpreting the gain in the scores of the students from the first (pre-evaluation) to the second quarter (post-evaluation). The results revealed that there was an increase in the post-evaluation with an average of 87.715 and a normalized gain of 0.122 inferred to a low gain and moderately effective towards the learning process. The researchers concluded that the preferred teaching practices were efficient as there is a gain in the students' scores and a responsiveness to equip the students in secondary school.

KEYWORDS: effectiveness, impact, preferred teaching practices, readiness, secondary school

INTRODUCTION

Subjects are different from each other and these differences led the teachers to change their preferred teaching practices; from section to section, and situation to situation. Preference means personal, but the subject, students, situation, and other factors are interchangeable, considering the conditions of preferences. In the present time, a lot of students are failing their classes even on the subject requirements due to the difficulty of the subjects as well as the transition of classroom instruction from primary school to secondary school. There are some teachers have already acquainted with their classroom strategies to guide the students in the class, to assure that they will get a benefit in the lesson, gaining more knowledge, value, and respect for others. According to Tavakoli and Baniasad-Azad (2017), effective teaching and teaching practices have a particular effect on how teachers approach the students as well as the development of the teaching-learning process. In this case, this study aimed to examine and identify the preferred teaching practices among selected Grade 7 junior high school subject teachers and its impact and effectiveness towards

the readiness of incoming Grade 7 students in secondary school.

In the Philippines, in the emergence of the K-12 Curriculum, the approach should be learner-centered, inclusive, developmentally relevant, and appropriate (Department of Education [DepEd], 2019). This approach to education puts the needs and interests of the students at the center of the teaching-learning process. In addition, the curriculum demands a relevant, responsive, and research-based approach based on learning theories, principles, sound research, and studies in teaching and learning dynamics. As this study addressed the demand, it also incorporated how effective teaching practices would be and how it affects the students' learning (Cooper, 2014); that is, a teaching practice connects students' engagement in the class. Further, these premises provide a perception of what preferred teaching practices would be along with an assumption in terms of its factors and reasons. Discussing the most preferred teaching practices of the teachers would also help other professional

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teachers and student-teachers to change or modify the approach to the students for effective learning.

As the students transitioned from childhood to adolescence, it is like a new starting point in their life, for the incoming Grade 7 students to be part of the secondary school curriculum. Because of this, certain factors are being considered by the teachers, especially for the Grade 7 level, on how they will prepare the students, teach the lessons, and assess the learning. Teachers used a wide variety of practices on how they will teach and deliver a lesson. On the other hand, students are changing and diverse for the teachers to address student-centered learning. This type of learning approach focuses on the needs, capabilities, interests, and other aspects of individual students, focusing more on students' aspects and considering their teaching practices. In this light, teachers need to assess if their preferred teaching practices will work on the students learning process considering the changes and diversity among them. A clear understanding of the relationship between effective teaching and teaching practices may contribute to the development of teaching standards and student learning Tavakoli and Baniasad-Azad (2017).

Significance of the Study

In discussing the preferred teaching practices of the teachers, this would help professional teachers and student-teachers to explore the needs of the students. This would give them a concept and knowledge of what could be the best and appropriate approach in delivering their lesson. Students will be able to understand why teachers have different practices and procedures in their class, helping them to be more open and grasp the differences among the approaches of teachers. In addition, Cooper (2014) identified the connection between the students' engagement inside the class and the teaching practices among the classes, in which teachers can easily modify and change their teaching practices with the help of a systematic and founded understanding of these practices. Further, teachers can use uniformed teaching practices to increase the engagement of the students inside the class and to prepare them in the secondary school curriculum.

Statement of the Problem

This study aimed to examine and identify the preferred teaching practices among selected Grade 7 junior high school subject teachers and its impact and effectiveness towards the readiness of incoming Grade 7 students in secondary school. Specifically, this study aimed to answer the following:

1. What are the preferred teaching practices among selected Grade 7 junior high school subject teachers in terms of the following:
 - A. classroom assessment,
 - B. class and lesson motivation,
 - C. teaching techniques, and
 - D. teaching routines?
2. What are the factors affecting the preferred teaching practices among selected Grade 7 junior high school subject teachers?
3. What are the consistencies and differences in the preferred teaching practices of selected Grade 7 junior high school subject teachers?

4. What is the impact and effectiveness of the preferred teaching practices towards the readiness of Grade 7 students in secondary school?
5. What are the initiatives of selected Grade 7 junior high school subject teachers in the utilization and evaluation of learning, learning difficulties, and learning styles?

LITERATURE REVIEW

This study is anchored on the policy guidelines of the K to 12 basic education program and on the Philippine's Republic Act No. 10533 otherwise known as the Enhanced Basic Education Act of 2013, in which one of the policy statements as prescribed by Republic Act No. 10533, the Department of Education shall adhere a learner-centered, inclusive, developmentally relevant, and appropriate curriculum (DepEd, 2019). This approach to education puts the needs and interests of the students at the center of the teaching-learning process demanding a relevant, responsive, and research-based approach based on learning theories, principles, sound research, and studies in teaching and learning dynamics. On the context of the transition from elementary education to the secondary school, one of its general functions is the preparation for a vocation or a higher level of education (Lacuesta, et. al., 1986), in which the foundation of education among the students should prepare them towards success as teachers explore various approaches, strategies, and methods for the learners' curricular experiences.

Teaching Approaches, Strategies, and Methods

The teaching method is a definite, an organized and systematic procedure which aims to facilitate learning and to achieve a specific aim of instruction (Asperas, 2005). A teaching method is effective when it has an impact both for the students and for the teachers as they grow inside and outside the classroom. It is effective as teachers became flexible in the methods and fields considering the capability of the students, and applying what is needed for the class. According to Cooper (2014), teachers can easily modify and change their teaching practices with the help of a systematic and founded understanding of teaching approach in emphasizing its utilization and outcome among the learners. In connection, Lynch and Star (2014) studied multiple teaching strategies that suit the teachers' way of giving instructions to the students as it implied a better learning experience.

Groschner, et. al. (2015), Bal (2016), and Kolesnikova (2016) also identified different approaches and methods to increase the students' academic success with the use of both an active learning and a traditional teaching method, called combined method, achievable alternatively than the traditional method alone. In this light, the modifications and changes in the pre-existing and new practices of teachers affect not only the nature of the method in terms of its development but also the learning process of the students in terms of its positive outcome and response. Aside from multiple and combined approaches, strategies such as project-based learning activities (Bakar, et. al., 2019), graphic design pedagogy in both analogue and digital education systems (Alhajri, 2016), experiential learning (Raja & Najmonnisa, 2018), and interactive methods including passive, active, and interactive teaching methods (Norin, et. al., 2018) are effective and evident towards students' learning process in building a better foundation of education and in helping them learn in various ways.

Perceptions towards the Teaching Practices

On the other hand, Kember and Kwan (2000) investigated the lecturers' conception of teaching and their teaching practices in which teachers' approaches to teaching were strongly influenced by their conceptions of excellent teaching; the process of transmitting knowledge tended to use content-centered approaches, and learning facilitation was more likely to use learning-centered approaches. This study implied that the conception or the preference of teachers greatly affects the students' outcome. In addition, Cao et. al. (2019) researched on the perception of teacher educators when it comes to their approaches in teaching in which knowledge transmission is one of the essential elements in the student-centered approach, but some teachers adopt both student and teacher-centered approach. Further, Schwab et. al. (2019) on the differentiation of teaching practices, Uibu et. al. (2017) on the students' social development of teachers mentoring experience, May et. al. (2017) on the classroom teaching practices, and Cabrillana and Mayan (2018) on the relationship of teaching styles with student achievement, also emphasized that teacher's way of teaching and its practices are related on how the achievements of the students can be, as they analyze whether modern or traditional teaching styles affect the students' achievements.

From these reviews, the researchers drew much of the processes in identifying the preferred teaching practices and procedures among the subject teachers towards the achievement and readiness of Grade 7 students in secondary school.

METHODOLOGY

This study used the sequential mixed method design in identifying the preferred teaching practices among selected Grade 7 junior high school subject teachers conducted at Espiritu Santo Parochial School of Manila, Inc., Manila, Philippines, and its impact and effectiveness towards the readiness of incoming Grade 7 students in the secondary school, for the school year 2019-2020. The research locale is exposed to the different factors that may contribute to the preferred teaching practices of the participants, the Grade 7 subject teachers. In terms of the readiness among Grade 7 students, the subject teachers identified teaching practices to address specific approaches in the transitional stage of the students from elementary (primary school) to junior high school (secondary school); both quantitative and qualitative methods were implemented in a sequential manner, through survey and interview, respectively.

The participants of this study were determined through purposive convenience sampling, a specific type of non-probability sampling method, which is selected based on convenient accessibility and proximity to the researchers as well as the characteristics of a population and the objective of the study (Tabuena, 2020) in identifying the preferred teaching practices, its flexibility, impact, and effectiveness towards the readiness of incoming Grade 7 students in secondary school.

In the first phase of the sequential mixed method (quantitative method), the research instrument (survey questionnaire) was evaluated and validated by three experts (teachers and coordinators) at Espiritu Santo Parochial School of Manila, Inc., and distributed for the survey process

among 12 teachers; consisting of three parts in terms of pedagogy, practices, and assessment and evaluation. In addition, the researchers asked permission to the participants to give necessary (existing) data, the class mean or average score of respective handled section/s both in the first and second grading periods. The data was used to assess whether the preferred teaching practices are effective and suitable for the students, particularly to Grade 7. The researchers initiated the strictest confidentiality and anonymity of the data gathered. In the second phase (qualitative method), an interview protocol was conducted to expound the data, involving a detailed exploration with a few individuals (Creswell, 2009).

The data are analyzed using the content analysis based on the interview and the use of frequency distribution, percentage, rank, and average/mean in determining the intensity of the response of the participants for each indicator in the survey questionnaire. On the other hand, to measure the existing data of the students taken from the teachers (class mean or average score of respective handled section/s both in first and second grading period), the researchers used the Hake factor analysis wherein the researchers obtained the value of normalized gain (gain of average) to interpret and analyze the gain in the scores of the students (Tabuena, 2019) from first quarter (pre-evaluation) to second quarter (post-evaluation).

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Preferred Teaching Practices among Selected Grade 7 Junior High School Subject Teachers

A. Preferred Teaching Practices on the Classroom Assessment

Table 1.1. Preferred Formative Assessment Practices among Grade 7 Subject Teachers

Formative Assessment	Frequency	Rank
Exercises	10	1
Group Activities	9	2.5
Informal Recitations	9	2.5
Homework	4	4
Others	2	5

Table 1.2. Preferred Summative Assessment Practices among Grade 7 Subject Teachers

Summative Assessment	Frequency	Rank
Quizzes	13	1
Final Projects	7	2.5
Standardized Test	7	2.5
Portfolios	4	4
Others	1	5

Tables 1.1 and 1.2 show the preferred formative and summative assessment practices among Grade 7 subject teachers, in which the most used assessments are exercises and quizzes, respectively. Exercise and quiz are both categorized as instructional strategies and resources in teaching a specific subject concept. Formative assessments such as group activities and recitations are some of the teaching techniques wherein a teacher applies certain methods to achieve an immediate objective. On the other hand, the least preferred formative and summative assessment practices are homework and portfolios. Teachers used a variety of practices in accordance with the specific method or mode of instructions.

B. Preferred Teaching Practices on the Class and Lesson Motivation

Table2. Preferred Motivation Practices among Grade 7 Subject Teachers

Motivations	Frequency	Rank
Activities	10	1
Rewards	8	2.5
Videos	8	2.5
Samples	6	4
Others	1	5

Table 2 shows the preferred motivation practices among Grade 7 subject teachers, in which the most used is the activities. Grade 7 subject teachers used activities such as games before and during the lesson proper. Subject teachers also used rewards or rewards systems such as the chits for the students to be motivated in the entire class. Other preferred motivation practices include videos and samples.

C. Preferred Teaching Practices on the Teaching echniques

Table3.1. Preferred Teaching Techniques Practices among Grade 7 Subject Teachers

Teaching Approaches	Frequency	Rank
Discussion	12	1
PowerPoint Presentation	11	2
Demonstration	7	3
Simulation	4	4

Table 3.1 shows the preferred teaching techniques practices among Grade 7 subject teachers, in which the most implemented is the discussion. Alongside the discussion, subject teachers used presentations such as PowerPoint to attract the students and engage them in the lesson. Subject teachers also practiced demonstration and simulation as teaching techniques. In this case, both traditional and modern (technological) way of delivering the lesson is evident among the subject teachers.

Table3.2. Preferred Teaching Routines Practices among Grade 7 Subject Teachers

Teaching Routines	Frequency	Rank
Review of previous lessons	14	1
Taking down notes	8	2
Summarization of lesson	6	3
Releasing a copy of presentation	1	4

In addition, Table 3.2 shows the preferred teaching routines practices among Grade 7 subject teachers aside from the usual teaching techniques. The other teaching practices utilized by subject teachers include a review of the previous lessons, as the most preferred teaching routine, taking down notes, summarization of the lesson, and releasing a copy of the presentation, respectively. The review of the previous lessons made the students remember their past lectures if ever the teachers are aligning or continuing it to the current lesson. It also prepares the students for the quizzes.

Further, subject teachers also used the common way of taking down notes for the students to have something to

read while they are at home. According to the subject teachers, some of their other teaching practices include collaborative learning, demonstration, and application. As shown in Table 3.2, the least classroom teaching routine is the distribution of a copy of the presentation. This practice, according to the subject teachers, makes the students shiftless and dependent on the material rather than in the actual and essential learning.

Factors Affecting the Preferred Teaching Practices among Selected Grade 7 Junior High School Subject Teachers

Based on the interview process, there are identified five bases and preferences on how subject teachers adjust or modify their teaching practices such as (a) the needs of the students, in terms of the capability to learn, to answer, and to understand, (b) the required modified curriculum for diverse learners, (c) the difficulty of the lesson, as the learners change their mood and interest, (d) the prescribed skills, especially for skill-based subjects like Sports, aligned with a collaborative and student-centered approach, and (e) the research-based teaching methods and techniques such as those prescribed in textbooks and other government-based materials.

Table4. Factors on the Preferred Practices among Grade 7 Subject Teachers

Factors	Frequency	Rank
Types of Learners	11	1
Subject Matter	6	2
School System	5	3
Curriculum	3	4
Salary	1	5.5
Others	1	5.5

Table 4 shows the factors on the preferred practices among grade 7 subject teachers. They prioritized the types of learners in deciding and implementing the type of teaching practices as they need to be flexible for the students. The subject matter is also a factor in choosing their teaching practices as it has different approaches for each subject and lesson, subject teachers adjust their preferences in contrast both in the subject and the preferred teaching practice. Other factors include the school system, the curriculum, and the salary. Salary affects the preferred teaching practices as the subjects teachers continuously develop their teaching techniques in terms of educational technology and other related techniques and skills.

Consistencies and Differences in the Preferred Teaching Practices among Selected Grade 7 Junior High School Subject Teachers

A. Consistencies on the Teaching Practices

Based on the interview, the consistencies on the teaching practices depend on the teaching-learning process, especially on the students' learning, and the flexibility of the classroom instructions. The following are the identified consistencies on the teaching practices to teach and help students to learn: making adjustments in accordance with the students such as the utilization of activities to the needs of the students; implementing varied and rich experiences in terms of the teaching routines such as the prayer, word or quote of the day, attendance, lesson proper, and assignment;

providing different teaching strategies in anticipating students' difficulties, doubts, and questions to address students' differences among sections; and relating students' varied concerns, in which the flexibility of the subject teachers is a major role to address the problem on culture sensitivity, the medium of instruction, and welfare among the students. Through these consistencies, students became more aware and prepare in the high levels of secondary school.

B. Differences in the Teaching Practices among Grade 7 Sections

On the other hand, differences in the teaching practices implied that there is no single approach, strategy, or method to implement among grade 7 sections, it is varied and eclectic in nature. Based on the interview, learning takes place on numerous activities corresponding to the capability of the students, the way on how students learn. The different teaching methods consist of various teaching techniques, and a single teaching technique could not be applied to all grade level sections because of the learning capabilities of the students, which is normally distinguished from high achievers or learners and low achievers or learners. In this case, one section could be advanced or modified in terms of the approach, strategy, or method, and adaptive techniques to different methods, for instance, an activity method could apply to all sections, yet different teaching techniques such as but not limited to, project, dramatization, role-playing, simulation, brainstorming, or debate could be implemented in a diversity of learners. In addition, one section could apply the lecture method to introduce concepts, yet for the more advanced section, it could be an integrated method.

The Impact and Effectiveness of the Preferred Teaching Practices towards the Readiness of Grade 7 Students in Secondary School

A. Performance of the Students in the First (Pre-Evaluation) and Second (Post Evaluation) Quarter

Table5. First and Second Quarter Grade Level Average among the Subjects

Grade 7 Subjects	Subject Mean (Grade Level Average)	
	First Quarter (%)	Second Quarter (%)
Araling Panlipunan ¹	86.74625	87.23375
Christian Living Education	87.32	88.435
English	81.3175	84.225
Filipino	84.145	85.37
ICT ²	86.785	89.285
Mathematics	89.72	91.74
General Average	86.006	87.715

Table 5 shows the first and second quarter grade level average among the subjects, in which all of the subjects specified were remarkably had an increase in the subject mean. It reveals that there was an increase in the students' performance in the post-evaluation after the preferred teaching practices assessment process with a mean score of 87.715%, remarked as "Very Satisfactory" according to the Department of Education Order No. 8, s. 2015.

Table6. The Gain of Average of the First and Second Quarter Grade Level Average among the Subjects

Quarter	General Average	Gain of Average	Inference
First Quarter (Pre Evaluation)	86.006	0.122	Low Gain
Second Quarter (Post Evaluation)	87.715		

From Table 5, in terms of the first quarter (pre-evaluation) and second quarter (post-evaluation) percentage, the obtained value of normalized gain (gain of average) as shown in Table 6, using the Hake factor, was 0.122 inferred to a low gain in scores of the students in the learning process with the used of the preferred teaching practices of the subject teachers. The result is a good standing in terms of the preferred teaching practices rather than no gain or negative result in the learning process of the students. Table 7 shows the range and inference in the gain of average by Hake (1998).

Table7. Gain of Average

Range	Inference	Interpretation
0.520 - above	High Gain	High Effective
0.231 - 0.519	Moderate Gain	Effective
0.000 - 0.230	Low Gain	Moderately Effective
< 0.000	No Gain	Not Effective

B. Performance of the Students in the Classroom Assessments

Table8. Formative and Summative Assessments Results of the Grade Level Sections

Descriptors	Classroom Assessments	
	Formative	Summative
Outstanding (5)	1	2
Very Satisfactory (4)	11	8
Satisfactory (3)	3	4
Fairly Satisfactory (2)	0	0
Did not meet expectations (1)	0	0
Weighted Mean	3.87	3.86
Interpretation	Very Satisfactory	Very Satisfactory

Table 8 shows the performance of the students in the second quarter, post-evaluation, in terms of formative and summative assessments. It reveals that both formative and summative assessments resulted in a very satisfactory remark, and the teaching practices were effective based on the assessment outcome.

C. The Impact of the Preferred Teaching Practices

The following are the impact of the preferred teaching practices among grade 7 subject teachers: (a) strategies may affect the way of the students learning process; (b) preferred teaching practices make the students remember and understand the lesson easier and to engage them in the lesson; (c) it helps the students to have experiential learning and giving clear insights for the lessons; (d) PowerPoint presentation helps them to illustrate and organize the teaching-learning procedure; (e) art of questioning helps the teacher to know the students better, and to realize the students for who they are as a person; (f) preferred teaching

practices as the most suitable method nowadays and effective teaching strategy, it helps the students to focus on the subject; and (g) it is really important to explain each lesson in any possible way. Through the aforementioned positive effects, it is implied that preferred teaching practices gave an avenue towards the readiness of grade 7 students in secondary school.

D. The Effectiveness of the Preferred Teaching Practices among Grade 7 Subject Teachers

On the other hand, the effectiveness of the preferred teaching practices among grade 7 subject teachers distinguished from the learning outcome of the students. Based on the interview, it is effective because students learn more by seeing and doing it on their own, and in terms of the average scores of the students, most of them passed the quizzes, long test, and periodical examinations, as it also exceeded the expectation from the standards and rubric measurements. These assessments ranged from satisfactory to outstanding outcomes as they easily understand each lesson. It is also evident that there is a low percentage of failures in both formative and summative assessment as shown in Table 8. In addition, assigning activities according to students' capability to organize things enable them to inculcate the values and attitudes that a human being should have. Based on the existing data and observation of the subject teachers, their preferred teaching practices were effective, as it supports the result from Table 6 inferred to a moderately effective in terms of the normalized gain (gain of average).

Initiatives in the Utilization and Evaluation of Learning, Learning Difficulties, and Learning Styles

As the students prepare for the higher levels in the secondary curriculum, the following are the initiatives of the teachers in the utilization of learning, learning difficulties, and learning styles: (a) developmentally appropriate strategies; (b) differentiated activities and instructional materials; (c) schematic processing (Tabuena, 2019), can be used as a cognitive shortcut - allowing the most common explanation to be chosen for new information; (c) modeling (games or activities); (d) creative teaching strategies (collaborative learning, inquiry-based instruction, and students' behavior management); and (e) socialized classroom art of questioning. The subjects teachers stated various ways when they teach their lesson and how they utilize the learning process. In general, teachers utilized learning, learning difficulties, and learning styles by recognizing and assessing their students, then applying the appropriate teaching practice to learn all of the students.

Evaluation of learning, learning difficulties, and learning styles also gives a clear direction of whether the students learned or not, and this learning has been applied. These directions in terms of evaluation greatly affect the readiness of the students towards the learning process. The following are the processes on evaluating students' learning: (a) immediate feedback in the form of activities or classroom assessments (formative and summative); (b) recitations and evaluative discussions; (c) practical and situational performance tasks (portfolios, theme paper, long test); and (d) rubric-based and applied tasks. Another factor is the type of learner. Thus, it affects the preference of the teacher in using the set initiatives and practices. The performance of the students justifies the effectiveness of the teaching

practices as there is an evident application from the aforementioned evaluative procedures.

Discussion

Some factors greatly affect the effectiveness of teachers' teaching methods. One of the factors is called tracking or ability grouping (Barrington, 2018). In this case, the students were assessed according to their overall performance, as it has positive and negative effects affecting their performance. Interviewed teachers stated that there are major differences in terms of delivering the lessons and conducting their practices between sections, a need to adjust the approach and the content of the lesson. This study supported the study of Cooper (2014) wherein teaching practices have a deep connection to the engagement of the students inside the classroom. This study showed that if the practice is effective, the students will be more engaged in the classroom, the goal of the current curriculum focusing on the student-centered processes; significant interrelationships could successfully attain and reach the desired end if teaching and effective learning take place (Salandanan, 2012).

CONCLUSIONS

The preferred teaching practices among selected Grade 7 junior high school subject teachers in terms of classroom assessment includes exercises and quizzes, as the most used assessments. Among other classroom assessments include group activities, informal recitations, homework, final projects, standardized test, and portfolios. In terms of class and lesson motivation, the most used is the activities, among others, include rewards, videos, and samples. In terms of teaching techniques the most implemented is the discussion, and among others include Powerpoint presentation, demonstration, and simulation. In terms of teaching routines the most preferred is the review of the previous lessons, and among others include taking down notes, summarization of the lesson, and releasing a copy of a presentation.

The most prioritized factor affecting the preferred teaching practices among selected Grade 7 junior high school subject teachers is the types of learners in deciding and implementing teaching practices, among others, include the subject matter, the school system, the curriculum, and the salary. The following are the identified consistencies on the teaching practices to teach and help students to learn: making adjustments in the utilization of activities, implementing varied and rich experiences, providing different teaching strategies, and relating students' varied concerns, for them to become more aware and prepare in the high levels of secondary school. On the other hand, differences in the teaching practices implied that there is no single approach, strategy, or method to implement among grade 7 sections, it is varied and eclectic in nature.

The performance of the students on the post-evaluation greatly affect the result of the assessment with a very satisfactory remark, and the teaching practices were effective based on the assessment outcome. In this case, preferred teaching practices affect the way of the students learning process, make them engage, focus, remember, and understand the lesson easier, endure experiential learning and give clear insights, illustrate and organize teaching-learning procedure, realize who they are as a person, and explain each lesson in any possible way. On the other hand, its effectiveness distinguished from the learning outcome of

the students as identified on the existing data and observation of the subject teachers inferred to a moderately effective in terms of the normalized gain. It is implied that the preferred teaching practices gave an avenue towards the readiness of grade 7 students in secondary school.

The initiatives of the teachers in the utilization of learning, learning difficulties, and learning styles include developmentally appropriate strategies, differentiated activities and instructional materials, schematic processing, modeling, creative teaching strategies, and socialized classroom art of questioning. The processes on evaluating students' learning include immediate feedback, recitations, and evaluative discussions, practical and situational performance tasks, and rubric-based and applied tasks. In general, teachers utilized these initiatives by recognizing and assessing their students and applying the appropriate teaching practices to learn and equip the students.

RECOMMENDATIONS

In light of the findings of the study, the researchers recommended to use appropriately the identified preferred teaching practices, venture the different kinds of learners and connect it with the possible teaching methods in a specific grade level to fully comprehend which method complements a type of learners, explore the teaching methods used in different grade levels to further expand the practices in the field of education, and further evaluate the practices of teachers for effective teaching and better learning.

REFERENCES

- [1] Alhajri, S. (2016). The effectiveness of teaching methods used in graphic design pedagogy in both analogue and digital education systems. *Universal Journal of Educational Research*, 4(2), 422-425.
- [2] Asperas, C. M. (2005). *Strategies of health education*. Educational Publishing House.
- [3] Bakar, N. I. A. et. al. (2019). Improving oral communicative competence in English using project-based learning activities. *English Language Teaching*, 12(4), 73-84.
- [4] Bal, A. P. (2016). The effect of the differentiated teaching approach in the algebraic learning field on students' academic achievements. *Eurasian Journal of Educational Research*, 63, 185-204.
- [5] Barrington, K. (2018, May 3). The pros and cons of tracking in schools. *Public School Review*. Retrieved from <https://www.publicschoolreview.com/blog/the-pros-and-cons-of-tracking-in-schools>
- [6] Cabrillana, A. H. & Mayan, C. L. (2018). Teaching styles and achievement: Student and teacher perspectives. *Economics of Education Review*, 67, 184-206.
- [7] Cao, Y. et. al. (2019). Teacher educators' approaches to teaching and connections with their perceptions of the closeness of their research and teaching. *Teaching and Teacher Education*, 85, 125-136.
- [8] Cooper, K. S. (2014). Eliciting engagement in the high school classroom: A mixed-methods examination of teaching practices. *American Educational Research Journal*, 51(2), 363-402.
- [9] Creswell, J. W. (2009). *Research design: Qualitative, quantitative, and mixed methods approaches* (3rd ed). SAGE Publications, Inc.
- [10] Department of Education (2019). DepEd Order No. 21 s. 2019, "Policy Guidelines on the K to 12 Basic Education Program." Pasig City: Department of Education.
- [11] Gröschner, A. et. al. (2015). Effects of a classroom discourse intervention on teachers' practice and students' motivation to learn mathematics and science. *Learning and Instruction*, 35, 94-103,
- [12] Hake, R. R. (1998). Interactive-engagement versus traditional methods: A six-thousand-student survey of mechanics test data for introductory physics courses. *American Journal of Physics*, 66(1), 64-74.
- [13] Kember, D. & Kwan, K. (2000). Lecturers' approaches to teaching and their relationship to conceptions of good teaching. *Instructional Science*, 28, 469-490.
- [14] Kolesnikova, I. V. (2016). Combined teaching method: An experimental study. *World Journal of Education*, 6(6), 51-59.
- [15] Lacuesta. et. al. (1986). *Historical, philosophical, and legal foundations of education (basic foundations of education II)*. Philippine Association for Teacher Education and Katha Publishing Co., Inc.
- [16] Lynch, K. & Star, J. R. (2014). Teachers' views about multiple strategies in middle and high school Mathematics. *Mathematical Thinking and Learning*, 16:2, 85-108.
- [17] May, D. E. et. al. (2017). Breaking the cycle: Future faculty begin teaching with learner-centered strategies after professional development. *CBE-Life Sciences Education*, 14(2), 1-12.
- [18] Norin, V. A., Norina, N. V. & Pukharenko, Y. V. (2018). Interactive methods of teaching at Russian engineering universities. *Educ Inf Technol*, 23, 2801-2820.
- [19] Raja, F. U. & Najmonnisa (2018). Comparing traditional teaching method and experiential teaching method using experimental research. *Journal of Education and Educational Development*, 5(2), 276-288.
- [20] Salandanan, G. G. (2012). *Elements of teaching*. Lorimar Publishing, Inc.
- [21] Schwab, S., Sharma U., & Hoffmann, L. (2019) How inclusive are the teaching practices of my German, Maths and English teachers? – psychometric properties of a newly developed scale to assess personalisation and differentiation in teaching practices. *International Journal of Inclusive Education*. <https://doi.org/10.1080/13603116.2019.1629121>
- [22] Tabuena, A. C. (2020). Perception of the students between the school's support in academics and sports towards the promotion and sustainability of sports activities. *International Journal of Trend in Scientific Research and Development*, 4(3), 630-634.
- [23] Tabuena, A. C. (2019). Effectiveness of classroom assessment techniques in improving performance of students in music and piano. *Global Researchers Journal*, 6(1), 68-78.
- [24] Tavakoli, M. & Baniasad-Azad, S. (2017). Teachers' conceptions of effective teaching and their teaching practices: a mixed-method approach. *Teachers and Teaching*, 23:6, 674-688.
- [25] Uibu, K. et. al. (2017). Beliefs about teaching held by student teachers and school-based teacher educators. *Teaching and Teacher Education*, 63, 396-404.